

Shielded bifunctional nanoreactor enabled tandem catalysis for plasma methane coupling

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The direct conversion of methane into valuable unsaturated C₂ hydrocarbons (C₂H₂ and C₂H₄) attracts growing attention. Non-thermal plasma offers a promising approach for this process under mild conditions. However, the competing formation of C₂H₆ and excessive dehydrogenation limit the selectivity toward C₂H₂ and C₂H₄. Herein, we develop a promising shielded bifunctional nanoreactor with a hollow structure and mesoporous channels (Na₂WO₄-Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂) that effectively limits CH₄ overactivation and promotes selective coupling to form C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ under plasma activation, achieving 39% CH₄ conversion with 42.3% C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ fraction. This nanoreactor features isolated Na₂WO₄ embedded within the channels and Mn₃O₄ confined in the cavity of the SiO₂ hollow nanospheres, enabling internal tandem catalysis at co-located active sites. Na₂WO₄ induces the conversion of diffused CH₄ and CH₃ into reactive intermediates ([•]CH and [•]CH₂), which subsequently couple on the Mn₃O₄ surface to form C₂H₂ and C₂H₄. Furthermore, the mesoporous channels inhibit the plasma discharge within the nanoreactor, preventing deep dehydrogenation of CH_x species to solid carbon. This nanoreactor demonstrates a highly selective route for the nonoxidative conversion of methane to valuable C₂ hydrocarbons, offering a new paradigm for the rational design of catalysts for plasma-driven chemical processes.

Unsaturated C₂ hydrocarbons, crucial building blocks in the chemical industry, are primarily produced from the energy-intensive processing of crude oil. The development of sustainable alternatives via gas conversion has attracted increasing interest^{1,2}. While conventional gas conversion methods rely on indirect syngas routes, direct methane conversion to unsaturated C₂ hydrocarbons offers a more attractive

pathway^{3,4}. Direct conversion of CH₄ to value-added fuels and chemicals can be achieved through either nonoxidative or oxidative catalytic routes⁵⁻⁷. The nonoxidative pathway offers high C₂ selectivity and atom utilization efficiency but demands endothermic conditions (up to 1100 °C), incurring substantial energy costs and CO₂ emissions¹. In contrast, oxidative coupling of methane (OCM) can significantly lower

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the reaction temperature to $-600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the presence of O_2 ^{8,9}. However, this method suffers from overoxidation of CH_4 to thermodynamically favored CO and CO_2 , limiting the yield of unsaturated C_2 hydrocarbons^{8,10}. These challenges highlight the urgent need for innovative strategies to enhance methane activation and coupling efficiency.

Non-thermal plasma (NTP) offers a promising solution for the homolytic activation of CH_4 into radicals, enabling nonoxidative coupling of methane (NOCM) under mild conditions^{11,12}. Among NTP techniques, dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) has been extensively explored for methane coupling. However, the main challenge is the limited control over product distribution, particularly in achieving selective production of unsaturated C_2 hydrocarbons, such as acetylene (C_2H_2) and ethylene (C_2H_4). Instead, ethane (C_2H_6) is predominantly produced in NOCM using DBD reactors^{11,13–16}. This selectivity issue originates from the significantly longer lifetime of CH_3 radicals ($>1\text{ ms}$) compared to CH_2 ($<30\text{ ns}$) and CH ($<5\text{ ns}$) radicals, which favors undesired reaction pathways¹⁷. Integrating tailored catalysts into DBD reactors has great potential to enhance selectivity toward targeted products^{14,18,19}. Ideally, such catalysts would regulate the dehydrogenation process and selectively stabilize CH and CH_2 intermediates, directing the reaction toward the formation of C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 .

The plasma-catalytic NOCM process involves heterogeneous surface reactions, highlighting the importance of the rational design of catalysts with tailored active sites and morphologies to maximize performance. In conventional OCM, Na_2WO_4 and Mn_2O_3 have proven effective in CH_4 activation and C-C coupling²⁰. Specifically, Na_2WO_4 generates reactive oxygen species to activate CH_4 , while Mn_2O_3 -supported O species promote the coupling of CH_3 intermediates^{21–23}. Given their critical roles in methane coupling, integrating Na_2WO_4 and Mn_2O_3 into plasma-catalytic NOCM offers a promising avenue to enhance the production of unsaturated C_2 hydrocarbons through their synergistic effects – a strategy that remains underexplored. Notably, Na_2WO_4 and Mn_2O_3 function at distinct stages of the methane coupling pathway. Plasma pre-activates CH_4 , facilitating Na_2WO_4 -mediated enhancement of CH_x dehydrogenation into CH and CH_2 surface species, while Mn_2O_3 promotes subsequent coupling of these intermediates to form C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 . Inspired by this synergistic interplay, we propose that a tandem plasma-catalysis system using spatially structured Na_2WO_4 - MnO_x catalysts—designed to sequentially optimize dehydrogenation and coupling steps—could potentially achieve enhanced efficiency in C_2 hydrocarbon formation compared to plasma-catalysis systems using randomly structured catalysts.

To address the challenges of overactivation and selectivity control in plasma-assisted methane coupling, we propose a promising assembled nanoreactor (Na_2WO_4 - Mn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 , denoted as WMO/m- SiO_2) designed for integration into a DBD plasma reactor (Supplementary Fig. 1). This nanoreactor features a hollow structure with mesoporous channels, accessibility to reactants both internally and externally. This design provides a shielding effect for CH_4 molecules within the channels, preventing excessive dehydrogenation by plasma-generated reactive species. Furthermore, the WMO/m- SiO_2 reactor demonstrates tandem catalytic functionality, significantly enhancing selectivity toward target C_2 products. Specifically, Na_2WO_4 located within the m- SiO_2 channels initiates CH_4 activation, generating CH_2 and CH surface intermediates. Concurrently, Mn_3O_4 species confined within the cavity of the SiO_2 spheres promote facile coupling of these CH and CH_2 intermediates to form C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 . Our study demonstrates significantly enhanced C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 yields compared to conventional catalysts under analogous DBD plasma conditions. This work offers a strategy to overcome critical limitations in plasma-catalysis, advancing efficient methane conversion to high-value C_2 hydrocarbons.

Results

Structural characterization of the catalysts

The synthesized mesoporous SiO_2 (m- SiO_2) featured interconnected nanospheres with diameters ranging from 95 to 135 nm (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Fig. 2a). Each nanosphere exhibited a hollow structure with a cavity diameter of $\sim 65\text{ nm}$ and a shell thickness of $\sim 20\text{ nm}$ (Supplementary Fig. 2b), along with a relatively high specific surface area of $240\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ (Supplementary Table 1). Loading manganese and tungsten species onto m- SiO_2 did not affect the hollow structure, and the resulting WMO/m- SiO_2 nanoreactor retained surface porosity with particles localized both within the cavity and on the external surface (Fig. 1b, d and Supplementary Fig. 3). X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the presence of Mn_3O_4 and amorphous SiO_2 in the WMO/m- SiO_2 composite (Supplementary Fig. 4). High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) revealed that the dispersed particles on the shell and cavity walls of m- SiO_2 were Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 , respectively (Fig. 1d–f and Supplementary Fig. 3). The measured lattice spacings of 0.38 and 0.25 nm corresponded to Na_2WO_4 (111) and Mn_3O_4 (211), respectively (Fig. 1e). Notably, although XRD confirmed the presence of Mn_3O_4 (Supplementary Fig. 4), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental distribution mapping (Supplementary Figs. 5, 6) of WMO/m- SiO_2 revealed negligible Mn and W signals compared to WMO/ SiO_2 and WMO/ZSM-5 (Zeolite Socony Mobil-5). Unless otherwise specified, WMO/m- SiO_2 , WMO/ SiO_2 , and WMO/ZSM-5 refer to samples with 1% Na_2WO_4 -5% Mn loaded on the support material. These findings indicate that Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 particles are predominantly encapsulated within the m- SiO_2 spheres. Additionally, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) scans in Fig. 1f further confirmed the presence of Mn species inside the m- SiO_2 cavity.

Plasma-catalytic NOCM reaction

We evaluated CH_4 conversion under three different conditions: plasma-only (no catalyst, no external heating), catalysis-only (external heating at $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, no plasma), and plasma-catalysis (coupled plasma and catalysts, no external heating). Under plasma-only and plasma-catalysis conditions, the measured temperature was $\sim 250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In plasma-only mode, C_2 - C_3 hydrocarbons dominated, with a maximum production of $31.2\text{ }\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$ at a CH_4 conversion of 33% (Supplementary Figs. 7, 8). Hydrocarbons with four or more carbon atoms were excluded due to negligible concentrations ($<5\%$ relative selectivity compared to C_2 products). Figure 1c shows the distributions of C_2H_4 and C_2H_2 within the C_2 - C_3 range. A synchronized increase in C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 proportions was observed, which can be attributed to the closely aligned energetic thresholds of electron-induced CH_4 conversion into CH_2 and CH species¹³. WMO/m- SiO_2 exhibited no catalytic activity for methane conversion at $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the absence of plasma. However, under NTP conditions with WMO/m- SiO_2 , the production of C_2H_4 and C_2H_2 significantly increased to $30.3\text{ }\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{ min}^{-1}$ ($12.8\text{ }\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{ min}^{-1}$ for C_2H_4 and $17.5\text{ }\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{ min}^{-1}$ for C_2H_2), surpassing WMO/ SiO_2 and WMO/ZSM-5 by factors of 5 and 3.4, respectively (Fig. 1c). With the WMO/m- SiO_2 nanoreactor, the proportion of unsaturated hydrocarbons in the C_2 - C_3 range increased significantly from 17.7% (plasma-only) to 42.3% (Fig. 1c and Supplementary Fig. 9). Simultaneously, the total yield of C_2H_4 increased markedly from 2.6 to $6.4\text{ }\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$, while C_2H_2 increased from 3.1 to $8.8\text{ }\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$. Notably, all three catalysts selectively promoted C_2H_4 and C_2H_2 production via deep dehydrogenation and coupling of CH_4 , rather than promoting overall methane conversion (Fig. 1h).

The pore sizes of m- SiO_2 and WMO/m- SiO_2 ranged from 20 to 40 nm, distinct from those of WMO/ SiO_2 and WMO/ZSM-5 (Fig. 1g and Supplementary Fig. 10). As shown in Supplementary Table 1, WMO/ZSM-5 exhibited the highest surface area of $226\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, significantly exceeding that of WMO/m- SiO_2 ($67\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$). However, plasma-only and

Fig. 1 | Characterization and catalytic performance. **a** TEM image and particle size distribution of $m\text{-SiO}_2$. **b** SEM image of $\text{WMO}/m\text{-SiO}_2$. **c** Production rate and molar fraction of C_2H_4 and C_2H_2 within $\text{C}_2\text{-C}_3$ hydrocarbons (Conditions: 1 bar, specific energy input (SEI) 5.1 kJ L^{-1} , where SEI is defined as plasma discharge power divided by the gas flow rate; Feed gas 5 vol% CH_4/Ar , total flow rate 200 mL min^{-1} , discharge power 17 W, experiment duration 60 min). Error bars (standard

deviation) in the figure were obtained from three sampling runs. **d, e** TEM and HRTEM images of $\text{WMO}/m\text{-SiO}_2$. **f** EDS line scans (from Point 1 to Point 2) from Fig. 1d. **g** Pore size distributions of $m\text{-SiO}_2$, $\text{WMO}/m\text{-SiO}_2$, $\text{WMO}/\text{ZSM-5}$, and WMO/SiO_2 . **h** Production rate of $\text{C}_2\text{-C}_3$ hydrocarbons and methane conversion for catalysis-only, plasma-only and plasma-catalysis systems.

plasma-catalysis conditions (using $\text{WMO}/\text{ZSM-5}$, WMO/SiO_2 and $\text{WMO}/m\text{-SiO}_2$) exhibited similar discharge properties (Supplementary Figs. 11–13). Additionally, packing the discharge zone with silica supports yielded consistent C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 levels (Supplementary Fig. 14). Furthermore, despite its lower surface area, $\text{WMO}/m\text{-SiO}_2$ demonstrated better CH_4 coupling efficiency to C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 , highlighting the critical role of its unique hollow mesoporous structure in enhancing the synergistic interaction between NTP and catalysis.

Evaluation of the effect of catalyst position on performance

TEM and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) images depict the morphology of the catalysts and the location of metal oxide particles, respectively (Fig. 2a and Supplementary Fig. 15). The metal oxide particles were selectively deposited in three configurations: (1) exclusively inside $m\text{-SiO}_2$ (In- $m\text{-SiO}_2$), (2) partially distributed within $m\text{-SiO}_2$ (Both- $m\text{-SiO}_2$), and (3) predominantly deposited on the exterior of $m\text{-SiO}_2$ (Out- $m\text{-SiO}_2$). For both “In- $m\text{-SiO}_2$ ” and “Both- $m\text{-SiO}_2$ ”, the Mn_3O_4 sizes ranged from 5 to 35 nm (Supplementary Fig. 15e, f).

TEM analysis of Both- $m\text{-SiO}_2$ revealed a significant reduction in the Si signal around Particle 1 (50–90 nm), while no similar decrease was observed near Particle 2 (150–200 nm) (Fig. 2a). Moreover, the Mn signal intensified in both particle types, suggesting that Particle 1 and Particle 2 are located on the exterior and interior surfaces of the $m\text{-SiO}_2$ nanosphere, respectively (Fig. 2a). XRD patterns further confirmed the spatial distribution of Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 particles. Samples with higher diffraction intensities and more pronounced peaks corresponded to increased exposure of Mn_3O_4 species on the external surface of $m\text{-SiO}_2$ (Supplementary Fig. 16).

EDS analysis of Particle 1 (internal) revealed weaker carbon and stronger oxygen signals compared to Particle 2 (external) (Fig. 2a and Supplementary Fig. 17). This suggests that $m\text{-SiO}_2$ protects Mn_3O_4 particles from direct exposure to CH_4 plasma. This shielding effect arises from the “Debye shielding” mechanism, where plasma discharge cannot penetrate the mesopores of $m\text{-SiO}_2$ due to their pore diameters being smaller than the Debye length (typically hundreds of nanometers)^{19,24,25}. Thus, the shielded internal cavity prevents the

Fig. 2 | Effect of catalyst location m-SiO₂ on NTP-CM performance. **a** TEM image and EDS spectra of spent catalysts In-m-SiO₂, Out-m-SiO₂, and Both-m-SiO₂ (after 60 min of reaction). **b** Schematic illustration of the role of m-SiO₂ and the effect of catalyst position on methane coupling. **c** Mn³⁺/(Mn³⁺+Mn²⁺) ratio for fresh and spent catalysts. **d** Yields of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ (defined as the product of CH₄ conversion and

the selectivity of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄) and equivalent carbon deposition rate (ECR, defined as the solid carbon selectivity on the catalyst divided by the methane conversion) (Conditions: 1 bar, SEI 5.1 kJ L⁻¹, total flow rate 200 mL min⁻¹, discharge power 17 W, experiment duration 60 min).

reduction of Mn₃O₄ particles and mitigates direct carbon deposition. This hypothesis is further supported by the observed decrease in the Mn³⁺/(Mn³⁺+Mn²⁺) ratio as more manganese oxide particles are located outside the m-SiO₂ layer (Fig. 2c and Supplementary Fig. 18). Previous studies have shown that low-valent metal catalysts (oxides, carbides, or metals) are highly effective for the deep dehydrogenation of CH₄^{26,27}. Consistent with these findings, Supplementary Fig. 19 shows that Mn₃O₄ particles exhibited a stronger carbon signal than the m-SiO₂ surface. Furthermore, as Na₂WO₄ and Mn₃O₄ particles are encapsulated within m-SiO₂ nanospheres, the yield of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ decreased from 7.0% (WMO/m-SiO₂) to 4.5% (Na₂WO₄-Mn₃O₄, denoted as WMO). This trend implies that converting an equivalent amount of methane leads to more carbon deposition when fewer encapsulated Na₂WO₄ and Mn₃O₄ particles are present (Fig. 2d and Supplementary Fig. 20).

The role of Na₂WO₄ and Mn₃O₄ in plasma-catalytic NOCM reaction

The 1% Na₂WO₄-5% Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ catalyst achieved a combined C₂H₄ and C₂H₂ selectivity of 18.1%, surpassing that of Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂ (14.5%), 5% Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ (13.2%) and plasma-only conditions (7.9%) (Fig. 3a and Supplementary Fig. 21). A comparison of CH₄ conversion and C₂-C₃ hydrocarbon distribution in the DBD reactor with previous studies is provided in Supplementary Table 2. The 1% Na₂WO₄-5% Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ (WMO/m-SiO₂) catalyst demonstrated the high selectivity for C₂H₂ and C₂H₄, while maintaining competitive methane conversion. Among reported studies, this work achieved a lower energy cost (EC) for CH₄ conversion (6.8 MJ/mol), demonstrating the effectiveness of the catalyst in plasma-catalytic NOCM reaction.

Notably, the catalyst exhibited stable performance for over 25 h (Supplementary Figs. 22, 23). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and XRD analyses confirmed that the dominant oxidation states of tungsten and manganese species in WMO/m-SiO₂, as well as in 5% Mn/m-SiO₂ and 1% Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂, remained unchanged after the reaction (Supplementary Figs. 24–26). Supplementary Fig. 21 shows that increasing the Na₂WO₄ loading from 0.5 to 5% increased carbon deposition from 16.4 to 24.6%. In contrast, higher Mn₃O₄ content reduced carbon deposition. These findings suggest that Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂ more effectively promotes the further dehydrogenation of methane compared to Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂.

The involvement of catalyst-bound oxygen species is well established in methane dehydrogenation^{5,9} and the coupling of intermediate species^{28–30}, highlighting their crucial roles in these reactions. To investigate this effect, we pretreated WMO/m-SiO₂ with H₂ at 450 °C for different durations, generating a series of WMO/m-SiO₂ samples with varying oxygen contents. H₂ pretreatment at 450 °C primarily reduced Mn₃O₄ but not tungsten species, as evidenced by H₂ temperature-programmed reduction (H₂-TPR) and XPS (Fig. 3c and Supplementary Figs. 27, 28). H₂ treatment resulted in increased carbon deposition and decreased selectivity for C₂H₄ and C₂H₂ when the WMO/m-SiO₂ nanoreactor was reduced for 5–20 min, accompanied by a decline in Mn³⁺ content and oxygen loading within the catalyst (Fig. 3b, c). These observations align with the trend that increasing the Mn content (β) from 2 to 10% in 1% Na₂WO₄-β Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ slightly enhanced the production of C₂-C₃ hydrocarbons (Supplementary Fig. 29). These findings suggest that MnO_x acts as an oxygen carrier, promoting the coupling of active species (CH_x and H) and reducing methane cracking. This highlights

Fig. 3 | Performance of Mn and W species. **a** Selectivity of products (carbon deposited on the catalyst, C₂H₄ and C₂H₂) for plasma-only and plasma-catalysis systems (Conditions: 1 bar, SEI 5.1 kJ L⁻¹, total flow rate 200 mL min⁻¹, discharge power 17 W, experiment duration 60 min). Error bars (standard deviation) in the figure were obtained from three sampling runs. **b** Selectivity of carbon deposited on the catalyst and selectivity of C₂H₄ and C₂H₂ for reduced WMO/m-SiO₂ (reduced at 450 °C with H₂). **c** Mn 2p XPS spectra of reduced WMO/m-SiO₂ (pretreated with

H₂ for 5, 10, 20, and 25 min). **d** IR spectra of WMO/m-SiO₂ (black), Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ (blue), and Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂ (red) under plasma-catalysis conditions. **e** Quasi-in situ DRIFT spectra of catalysts after plasma-catalytic NOCM reaction. **f** CH₂D₂ and C₂HD₃ species generated under plasma-only and plasma-catalysis (with WMO/m-SiO₂) conditions (feed gas 2.5 vol% CH₄-2.5 vol% CD₄/Ar, SEI 5.1 kJ L⁻¹, total flow rate 200 mL min⁻¹; experiment duration 60 min).

the importance of optimizing oxygen content in catalysts to maximize performance.

CH_x species absorbed on the catalyst and in the gas phase

In situ plasma-coupled Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was used to investigate plasma-assisted surface reactions on WMO/m-SiO₂, 5% Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ and 1% Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂. As shown in Supplementary Fig. 30, the intensities of the IR peaks at 628 cm⁻¹ (≡C-H) and 950 cm⁻¹ (=C-H) decreased as the reaction progressed. These absorbed ≡C-H and =C-H bands are associated with key intermediates involved in the formation of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ during the catalytic process³¹. Additional IR bands at 1465, 1585, 1708, 3265, and 3320 cm⁻¹ correspond to C=C stretching vibrations on the catalyst surface (Fig. 3d)^{31–33}. Notably, WMO/m-SiO₂ exhibited the highest intensities for peaks associated with ≡C-H, =C-H, and C=C compared to catalysts containing only Mn or W. This finding suggests that the synergistic interaction between Mn₃O₄ and Na₂WO₄ sites effectively promotes the formation of surface-adsorbed [•]CH and [•]CH₂ groups, ultimately enhancing the yield of C₂H₄ and C₂H₂.

Quasi-in situ DRIFTS characterization provided further insights into the types of adsorbed species remaining on the catalyst surface after the reaction (Supplementary Figs. 31, 32). As shown in Fig. 3e, several key peaks were observed, including C–H stretching from [•]CH₃ (2960 and 2872 cm⁻¹)³⁴, C–H stretching from [•]CH₂ (2930 cm⁻¹)³⁴, C=C bonds (1585 and 1465 cm⁻¹)^{32,33} and C-H bond bending/deformation modes (1384 cm⁻¹)³⁵. In this study, the angles (Δ1 = 12°, Δ2 = 0°, and Δ3 = 3°) between the standard slope and tangents (peak 2960 to peak 2930 cm⁻¹) were used to measure the relative proportions of adsorbed

[•]CH₃ and [•]CH₂ species on the catalyst surface. These species serve as precursors for the formation of ethane and ethylene, respectively³⁶. Among the catalysts, 1% Na₂WO₄-5% Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ exhibited the highest [•]CH₂ intensity, followed by 1% Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂ and 5% Mn/m-SiO₂. Notably, compared to 1% Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂, 5% Mn/m-SiO₂ promoted the formation of surface C=C (1585 and 1465 cm⁻¹), indicating that [•]CH₂ formation predominantly occurred at W sites, while Mn sites facilitated the coupling of CH₂ to form C=C bonds. Although the internal Mn₃O₄ sites are not directly exposed to plasma (Supplementary Fig. 3), varying the Mn₃O₄ loading within the m-SiO₂ spheres led to observable changes in product distribution and the relative intensity of adsorbed [•]CH₃ and [•]CH₂ species (Supplementary Figs. 21, 31). This suggests that CH_x radicals can diffuse or migrate at least 20 nm to reach Mn₃O₄ sites within their lifetime, enabling them to access the interior of the catalyst for subsequent reactions.

Methane isotopic labeling experiments

Methane isotopic labeling experiments, conducted using a parallel flow of CH₄ and CD₄, revealed an increase in CH₃ and CH₂ radicals during the plasma-catalyzed reaction over WMO/m-SiO₂ compared to the plasma-only condition (Fig. 3f). Detailed experimental procedures are provided in the Methods section, and the corresponding conversions of CD₄ and CH₄, along with product distributions, are shown in Supplementary Fig. 33. The experiment was designed to probe the complex dynamics within the discharge field, where multiple collisions and coupling reactions occur, leading to the reversible activation of C-H bonds, facilitating the reformation of nascent methane from activated C_xH_y intermediates³⁶. This behavior contrasts with the

Fig. 4 | The structures of WMO/m-SiO₂ and DFT calculations. **a** Fourier transform (FT) of the EXAFS spectrum of Mn and the DFT-optimized structure of Mn₃O₄ on WMO/m-SiO₂. **b** FT-EXAFS spectra of W and DFT-optimized structure of Na₂WO₄ on WMO/m-SiO₂. **c** DFT-optimized geometries of [•]CH₄ dehydrogenation to [•]CH₃, [•]CH₂, and [•]CH on Mn₃O₄ (211) and Na₂WO₄ (111) surfaces. **d** DFT-optimized geometries of [•]CH₃ to C₂H₄ on Mn₃O₄ (211) and Na₂WO₄ (111) surfaces. **e** DFT-optimized geometries of [•]CH₂ coupled to C₂H₂ on Mn₃O₄ (211) and Na₂WO₄ (111) surfaces. **f** DFT-optimized geometries of intermediates in the plasma-catalytic conversion of CH₄ to radicals, C₂H₂, C₂H₄, and C₂H₆. **g** Wavelet transform plots of the Mn K-edge and W K-edge. **h** Schematic illustration of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ formation pathways on WMO/m-SiO₂.

essentially irreversible C-H activation in traditional OCM²⁹. The detection of mixed CH₂D₂ and CHD₃ isotopes during plasma-catalyzed NOCM on WMO/m-SiO₂ confirmed this mechanism. Compared to the plasma-only system, the plasma-catalytic system with WMO/m-SiO₂ demonstrated significantly higher production of CH₂D₂ and CHD₃ (Fig. 3f). This result suggests that WMO/m-SiO₂ enhances the activation of CH₄ and the generation of CH₃/CD₃ and CH₂/CD₂ radicals. The enriched pool of CH₂ species ultimately promotes dimerization into C₂H₂ and C₂H₄¹¹. In summary, the synergistic interaction between Mn₃O₄ and Na₂WO₄ sites in the WMO/m-SiO₂ nanoreactor effectively promotes the formation of surface-adsorbed [•]CH and [•]CH₂ species, as well as gas-phase CH₂ radicals, leading to enhanced yields of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄.

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations

Synchrotron radiation-based X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) was employed to elucidate the chemical state and local structure of the WMO/m-SiO₂ catalysts. The X-ray absorption near-edge structure (XANES) spectra at the Mn K-edge (Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂) and W K-edge (Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂) in WMO/m-SiO₂ closely resembled those of the

individual Mn₃O₄/m-SiO₂ and Na₂WO₄/m-SiO₂ reference catalysts (Supplementary Fig. 34). This observation, in substantial contrast to the combined Na₂WO₄-Mn₃O₄ spectrum, strongly suggests the presence of isolated Mn₃O₄ and Na₂WO₄ active sites dispersed on the m-SiO₂ support. Further validation was provided by Fourier transform (FT) extended X-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy (EXAFS) results (Fig. 4a, b). The peaks at 1.4 Å (Fig. 4a) and 1.2 Å (Fig. 4b) mainly represent the single scattering of Mn-O and W-O bonds, respectively, confirming the existence of isolated Mn and W species and the absence of direct Mn-W binding in the WMO/m-SiO₂ catalyst. The bond lengths for Mn-O and W-O in WMO/m-SiO₂ were determined to be 1.86 and 1.69 Å, respectively (Supplementary Table 3). The proposed Mn-O model exhibited excellent agreement with the experimental spectra, as evidenced by its superior fit in the XANES analysis and negligible deviations from DFT calculations (Supplementary Figs. 34–36).

To elucidate the fundamental mechanism of C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ production within WMO/m-SiO₂, spin-polarized periodic DFT calculations were employed to unravel the distinct roles of its components during plasma-catalytic NOCM reaction. Based on experimental results

(Fig. 1e and Supplementary Fig. 3), we selected Mn_3O_4 (211) and Na_2WO_4 (111) surfaces as model systems (Supplementary Fig. 35). The calculated binding energies of reaction intermediates involved in CH_4 dehydrogenation and subsequent coupling to C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 are presented in Supplementary Tables 4, 5. Notably, the binding strength of the C_xH_y intermediates followed the order of Mn_3O_4 (211) > Na_2WO_4 (111), with intermediates binding via C or C-C on both surfaces (Supplementary Figs. 37, 38 and Supplementary Tables S4, S5).

The calculated Gibbs free energy change profiles for CH_4 dehydrogenation and intermediate active species coupling on the Mn_3O_4 (211) and Na_2WO_4 (111) catalysts are shown in Fig. 4c–e. For CH_4 dehydrogenation (Fig. 4c), the Na_2WO_4 (111) surface can facilitate CH_4 dehydrogenation to produce $\cdot\text{CH}_3$, $\cdot\text{CH}_2$, and $\cdot\text{CH}$ species. The most challenging step was $\cdot\text{CH}_3$ dehydrogenation, with an uphill energy of 0.22 eV, followed by $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ dehydrogenation, with an uphill energy of 0.19 eV on the Na_2WO_4 (111) surface. In contrast, CH_4 dehydrogenation on the Mn_3O_4 (211) surface required significantly higher uphill energy (0.73 and 0.75 eV) for producing $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ and $\cdot\text{CH}$ species, respectively. In addition, the reaction energy barriers for $\cdot\text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \cdot\text{CH}_2 + \text{H}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2 \rightarrow \cdot\text{CH} + \text{H}$ were calculated (Supplementary Table 8). These two elementary reactions were identified as the rate-determining steps in CH_4 dehydrogenation to generate $\cdot\text{CH}_3$, $\cdot\text{CH}_2$, and $\cdot\text{CH}$ species on both surfaces (Fig. 4c), with energy barriers of 0.97 and 0.69 eV on Na_2WO_4 (111), significantly lower than those on Mn_3O_4 (211) (1.93 and 2.02 eV). This indicates that the Na_2WO_4 (111) surface is more effective in facilitating CH_4 dehydrogenation, consistent with experimental results (Supplementary Fig. 21). The Mn_3O_4 (211) surface was found to be more favorable for coupling $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ and $\cdot\text{CH}$ species to generate C_2H_4 and C_2H_2 (Fig. 4d, e). The most challenging steps were the desorption of $\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ (Fig. 4d) and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ dehydrogenation (Fig. 4e), with uphill energies of 0.49 and 0.19 eV, respectively. In contrast, on the Na_2WO_4 (111) surface, the most difficult steps were $\cdot\text{CH}_3$ dehydrogenation (Fig. 4d) and desorption of $\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$ (Fig. 4e), with significantly higher uphill energies of 0.73 and 2.52 eV, respectively. In addition, we investigated CH_4 dehydrogenation and radical coupling reactions under plasma-only conditions (Fig. 4f). The results suggest that plasma-driven NOCM without a catalyst favors the production of C_2H_6 , in stark contrast to plasma-catalyzed reactions.

To elucidate the role of SiO_2 in the WMO/m- SiO_2 nanoreactor, $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ (211) and $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4$ (111) models were built (Supplementary Figs. 36, 39, 40). The calculated binding energies of reaction intermediates involved in CH_4 dehydrogenation and subsequent coupling to form C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 are presented in Supplementary Tables 6 and 7, with the most stable adsorption configurations illustrated in Supplementary Figs. 39, 40. Notably, $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4$ (111) exhibited significantly weaker binding for $\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$ compared to the isolated Na_2WO_4 (111) surface, with adsorption energies of -0.54 versus -0.95 eV, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 41 and Supplementary Tables 6, 7). In contrast, $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ (211) favored the desorption of $\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ compared to pure Mn_3O_4 (211), with an adsorption energy of -0.62 eV (compared to -1.58 eV on pure Na_2WO_4 (111)). The binding energies of $\cdot\text{CH}/\text{CH}_2$ on $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ (211) and $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4$ (111) were -6.75 and -5.77 eV and -2.61 and -5.43 eV, respectively, indicating that $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ has a stronger adsorption capacity for $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ and $\cdot\text{CH}$ than $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4$. In summary, DFT calculations reveal that Na_2WO_4 facilitates CH_4 dehydrogenation to $\cdot\text{CH}$ or $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ intermediates, while Mn_3O_4 promotes the coupling of $\cdot\text{CH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ to form C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 , respectively. Furthermore, the presence of SiO_2 in combination with Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 enhances the desorption of the generated $\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$ and $\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ species. These findings are consistent with experimental observations.

Reaction mechanisms

The enhanced catalytic performance of $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4\text{-Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$, compared to $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$ and $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$, highlights the

synergistic effects between Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 sites (Supplementary Fig. 21). Quasi-in situ DRIFTS characterization (Fig. 3e and Supplementary Figs. 31, 32) indicates that W sites promote $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ generation, while Mn sites facilitate the coupling of $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ to form C=C bonds.

If radicals were fully converted at Na_2WO_4 before reaching Mn_3O_4 sites within m- SiO_2 , significant carbon deposition would be expected on Na_2WO_4 . However, compared to $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$, the 1% $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4\text{-5% Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$ catalyst exhibits lower carbon accumulation (Supplementary Fig. 21) and higher $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ and C=C intensities (Fig. 3e). These findings suggest that radicals initially generated on Na_2WO_4 sites undergo further transformation into $\cdot\text{CH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$, which subsequently migrate to Mn_3O_4 sites for coupling reactions to produce C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 .

Wavelet transforms of the EXAFS spectra at the Mn K-edge and W K-edge for WMO/m- SiO_2 , 5% $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$, and 1% $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{m-SiO}_2$ reveal similar Mn–O and W–O scattering peaks at (4.1, 1.4 Å) and (3.9, 1.2 Å), respectively (Fig. 4g). These findings indicate that Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 are independently distributed on the m- SiO_2 support, consistent with TEM observations (Supplementary Fig. 3). Notably, TEM analysis also demonstrates the close spatial proximity of Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 , providing potential pathways for intermediate species migration.

DFT calculations further reveal that the adsorption energies of $\cdot\text{CH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ on Mn_3O_4 are -5.21 and -3.96 eV, respectively, significantly stronger than those on Na_2WO_4 (-3.27 and -3.08 eV) (Supplementary Tables 6, 7). Notably, when supported on m- SiO_2 , the adsorption energy gap increases, suggesting that radicals preferentially stabilize on Mn_3O_4 rather than remaining on Na_2WO_4 (Supplementary Fig. 41). This thermodynamic preference, combined with the close proximity of two active sites, indicates that $\cdot\text{CH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ species likely undergo surface diffusion or desorption-reabsorption migration, facilitating C-C coupling on Mn_3O_4 . Similar bifunctional catalysis mechanisms have been reported in thermal catalysis systems, where intermediate spillover between distinct active sites enhances reaction efficiency^{37,38}.

The distribution and synergy between Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 sites further facilitate the sequential activation of C-H bonds and C-C coupling within the WMO/m- SiO_2 nanoreactor. Herein, a tandem reaction mechanism is proposed for CH_4 conversion to C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 (Fig. 3h): (I) CH_4 dissociation and CH_3 diffusion: Energetic electrons from the plasma induce CH_4 dissociation into CH_x fragments, which subsequently diffuse toward the interior of the silica sphere due to the concentration gradient across m- SiO_2 . (II) Dehydrogenation at Na_2WO_4 sites (support on the channel): $\cdot\text{CH}_3$ species undergo dehydrogenation at W sites, forming surface-adsorbed $\cdot\text{CH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ species. (III) Surface species coupling on Mn sites: $\cdot\text{CH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2$ species migrate from Na_2WO_4 to Mn_3O_4 sites, leading to C-C coupling for C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 production.

Notably, the mesoporous channels of m- SiO_2 restrict plasma penetration into the interior of m- SiO_2 , thereby mitigating excessive CH_4 activation (e.g., methane cracking) and suppressing carbon deposition. This structural confinement, combined with the synergistic tandem catalysis of Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 , significantly enhances the yield of C_2 products. Moreover, the shielding effect of the nanoreactor reduces plasma-induced product decomposition and recombination, further enhancing selectivity.

Discussion

This work presents a promising nanoreactor catalyst design strategy that significantly improves the yield and selectivity of C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 through plasma-catalytic NOCM under mild conditions. The nanoreactor features a hollow nanosphere structure with Na_2WO_4 nanoparticles anchored on the interconnected channels and monodispersed Mn_3O_4 nanocrystals hosted within the internal cavity. By positioning the nanoreactors in the discharge area, methane conversion reached

34%, with a selectivity of 42.3% toward C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 . This represents a nearly 4.5-fold increase in yield and a fourfold increase in selectivity for unsaturated C_2 hydrocarbons compared to the plasma-only system. Importantly, no deactivation was observed during the 25-h catalyst stability test. Mechanistic investigations revealed that Na_2WO_4 promotes the dehydrogenation of diffused CH_4 and CH_3 , leading to the formation of $\cdot CH$ and $\cdot CH_2$ intermediates. These species subsequently undergo C-C coupling on the Mn_3O_4 surface to form C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 . The excellent catalytic performance, supported by in situ plasma-coupled FTIR characterization, is further corroborated by DFT calculations. These calculations demonstrate that a tandem catalytic effect is achieved through the isolated Na_2WO_4 and Mn_3O_4 active sites, which are responsible for the enhanced selectivity. Furthermore, the mesoporous nanoreactor design prevents the reduction of internal Mn_3O_4 by CH_4 plasma through the Debye shielding effect. This reduces carbon deposition on the catalyst and protects the generated $\cdot CH$ and $\cdot CH_2$ intermediates from further decomposition due to the absence of plasma discharge within the mesopores. This catalyst design strategy offers significant potential for advancing plasma-catalysis. It enables highly selective and directional conversion, improving the energy efficiency of plasma-catalytic systems and paving the way for a high-value route to transform methane into unsaturated light olefins under mild conditions.

Methods

Synthesis of SiO_2 nanospheres

Mesoporous SiO_2 (m- SiO_2) was synthesized using a double template method in an ethanol solution. First, ethanol and polyacrylic acid were added to a vial and stirred for 30 min. Then, diluted ammonia water was added to the above solution, followed by the introduction of polyether, and the mixture was stirred for another 30 min. After that, ethyl orthosilicate was added dropwise to the vial, resulting in a suspension after 4 h of stirring. Subsequently, the suspension was centrifuged and washed three times with ethanol. Finally, the precursors were evaporated overnight and calcination at 550 °C.

Synthesis of αNa_2WO_4 - βMn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2

αNa_2WO_4 /m- SiO_2 , βMn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 , and αNa_2WO_4 - βMn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 (where α and β denote the respective weight percentages of each metal oxide) were synthesized using the incipient wetness method. The Mn loading on the m- SiO_2 support varied from 2 to 10 wt% (2, 5, 7.5, and 10 wt%), while the Na_2WO_4 loading ranged from 0.5 to 5% (0.5, 1, 2, and 5 wt%). For the preparation of Na_2WO_4 /m- SiO_2 and Mn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 , aqueous solutions of manganese nitrate tetrahydrate ($Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$) or sodium tungstate dihydrate ($Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$) were mixed with m- SiO_2 in a water bath. The mixture was stirred until it reached a paste-like consistency and then dried overnight at 70 °C. Subsequently, the dried samples were calcined in air at 550 °C. A two-step impregnation method was used for the synthesis of βNa_2WO_4 - αMn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 (denoted as WMO/m- SiO_2). First, Mn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 was prepared as described above. Then, Na_2WO_4 was loaded onto the Mn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 using the same drying and calcination procedures. This method was also used to prepare 1% Na_2WO_4 -5% Mn_3O_4 / SiO_2 and 1% Na_2WO_4 -5% Mn_3O_4 /ZSM-5. Before testing, all catalysts were crushed and sieved to obtain particles with sizes between 30 and 60 mesh.

Synthesis of Mn_3O_4 -deposited m- SiO_2 catalysts

Three types of catalysts with varying Mn_3O_4 locations were prepared: In-m- SiO_2 , where Mn_3O_4 was deposited exclusively within the mesopores of m- SiO_2 ; Both-m- SiO_2 , where Mn_3O_4 was partially distributed within the mesopores and on the exterior surface of m- SiO_2 ; Out-m- SiO_2 , where Mn_3O_4 was primarily located on the exterior surface of m- SiO_2 . In-m- SiO_2 was synthesized as described above. Both-m- SiO_2 was prepared using a rapid heating and drying method, where Na_2WO_4

was first loaded onto m- SiO_2 , followed by the deposition of Mn_3O_4 . The precursors were rapidly heated from room temperature to 300 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C min^{-1} for 2 h and then calcined at 550 °C. Out-m- SiO_2 was synthesized by mechanically mixing pre-synthesized Mn-O and Na-W-O precursors. Specifically, solutions of Mn or W were dissolved in deionized water and stirred at 50 °C for 3 h. After drying overnight, the precursors were mechanically mixed with m- SiO_2 and calcined at 550 °C.

Catalyst activity test

The performance of the catalyst in the thermal catalytic NOCM reaction (denoted as catalyst only) was evaluated in a DBD reactor (plasma off) equipped with heating tape and operated at atmospheric pressure. The reactor was loaded with 1% Na_2WO_4 -5% Mn_3O_4 /m- SiO_2 and secured with quartz wool on both ends. Prior to testing, the catalyst was pretreated with argon (200 mL min^{-1}) at 100 °C for 20 min to remove impurities. The temperature was then increased to 250 °C and monitored using a K-type thermocouple placed within the catalyst bed. A diluted methane feed (5 vol% CH_4 in Ar) at a total flow rate of 200 mL min^{-1} was used to minimize mass transfer limitations and accurately evaluate the intrinsic catalytic activity. The feed gas was preheated to 30 °C, and the experiments were conducted for 60 min.

For plasma-catalysis and plasma-only conditions, the DBD reactor was operated without external heating. The experimental procedure involved the following steps: (1) The catalyst was pretreated with argon (100 mL min^{-1}) at 100 °C for 20 min, followed by cooling to room temperature. (2) A 5 vol% CH_4 /Ar mixture (200 mL min^{-1}) flowed through the DBD reactor for 10 min before switching on the plasma. (3) The plasma was ignited at an SEI of 5.1 kJ L^{-1} (calculated as the discharge power divided by the gas flow rate) and maintained at a discharge power of 17 W with a flow rate of 200 mL min^{-1} for 60 min. (4) After switching off the plasma, the DBD reactor was purged with argon (100 mL min^{-1}) for 10 min. (5) The spent catalyst was removed, and a 10 vol% O_2 /Ar mixture (100 mL min^{-1}) was introduced to oxidize solid carbon deposited in the DBD reactor. This step was carried out at an SEI of 6.14 kJ L^{-1} until no CO or CO_2 was detected in the exhaust gas. (6) The spent catalyst was reintroduced into the cleaned reactor, and a 10 vol% O_2 /Ar mixture (100 mL min^{-1}) was used to oxidize carbon deposited on the catalyst. This step was continued, and no CO or CO_2 were detected in the exhaust gas. The amount of carbon deposited was calculated using the equation $N_C = V \times (C_{CO_2} + C_{CO}) \times 22.4$, where V is the total volume of exhaust gas during the oxidation process, and C_{CO_2} and C_{CO} are the concentrations of CO_2 and CO in the exhaust gas, respectively. To avoid interfering with the plasma field, the reactor temperature was measured using an infrared thermometer.

Isotopic labeling experiments

To investigate the relative contributions of CH_2 and CH_3 radicals to CH_4 decomposition, isotopic labeling experiments were conducted. The catalyst was first pretreated in a 5 vol% CH_4 /Ar mixture (discharge power 17 W, flow rate 200 mL min^{-1}) for 60 min and then cooled to room temperature. Next, argon (200 mL min^{-1}) was flowed through the reactor for 10 min to purge residual gases. A gas mixture of 2.5 vol% CD_4 and 2.5 vol% CH_4 in argon (200 mL min^{-1}) was subsequently introduced into the DBD reactor for 10 min. The plasma was then switched on and sustained for 60 min, during which mass spectrometric signals at $m/z = 15, 18, \text{ and } 19$ were monitored. The concentrations of CH_4 and CD_4 in the mixture were determined using mass spectrometry. From these measurements, the conversion of CH_4 and CD_4 , as well as the selectivity of the product, was determined. Under plasma discharge conditions, CH_4 and CD_4 dissociate into radicals including CH_3 , CH_2 , CH , CD_3 , CD_2 , CD , H, and D. These radicals recombine to form isotopically labeled methane species, such as CD_3H

($m/z = 19$), and CD_2H_2 ($m/z = 18$). The formation of CD_3H and CD_2H_2 results from the recombination reactions of CD_3 with H and CD_2 with two H atoms, respectively. The signals at $m/z = 15$ and $m/z = 19$ reflect the concentrations of CH_4 and CD_3H , respectively. When analyzing the peak intensity of CD_2H_2 , it is critical to consider the contribution of CD_4 fragmentation ($m/z = 20$), which generates CD_3 ($m/z = 18$). Specifically, the signal at $m/z = 18$ reflects contributions from both CD_2H_2 and the CD_3 fragment derived from CD_4 fragmentation.

In situ plasma-coupled FTIR characterization

To elucidate plasma-induced surface reactions during the plasma-catalytic NOCM process, we employed in situ plasma-coupled FTIR spectroscopy using a custom-designed plasma gas cell¹⁹. The experimental procedure is described in detail as follows: (I) Prior to analysis, each sample was pretreated with argon plasma (99.999% purity) at a flow rate of 100 mL min^{-1} in a DBD reactor at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 min to remove residual surface species. (II) A 5% CH_4/Ar mixture (40 mL min^{-1}) was introduced to purge the cell for 30 min. During this step, the temperature was decreased from 100 to $35\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, after which the IR background spectrum was collected. (III) The plasma was switched on, and the plasma-catalytic NOCM was conducted for 15 min. (IV) After switching off the gas flow, IR spectra were collected every 3 min for a total duration of 18 min.

Quasi-in situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFT) analysis was conducted using an FTIR spectrometer (IS50, Thermo Fisher Co. Ltd.) equipped with a liquid nitrogen N_2 -cooled mercury-cadmium-telluride (MCT) detector. The background spectrum was obtained by pretreating the catalyst with Ar plasma in a DBD reactor under conditions identical to those used in the plasma-catalytic NOCM experiments ($SEI = 5.1\text{ kJ L}^{-1}$, flow rate = 200 mL min^{-1}). Following pretreatment, the catalyst was cooled to room temperature before conducting the quasi-in situ DRIFTS measurements. To avoid air exposure, the pretreated catalysts were transferred from the DBD reactor to the DRIFT cell within a glovebox. For the plasma-catalytic NOCM reaction, the plasma was switched off after the experiment, and the inlet and outlet of the DBD reactor were sealed. Subsequently, the spent catalysts were then transferred from the DBD reactor to the DRIFT cell within a glovebox, and IR spectra were collected at room temperature.

Computational details

Spin-polarized density functional theory (DFT)^{39,40} calculations were performed using the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP) code⁴¹. The exchange-correlation interactions between electrons were described using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA)^{42,43}. Following convergence tests, plane-wave pseudopotentials with kinetic cutoff energy of 420 eV ⁴⁴ for Mn_3O_4 and 500 eV ⁴⁵ for Na_2WO_4 method were employed within the projector augmented wave (PAW) method. The Mn_3O_4 (211) and Na_2WO_4 (111) surfaces were selected as the computational models based on the experimental results (Fig. 1e and Supplementary Fig. 3). To minimize interactions between the slab and its periodic images, a vacuum layer of -15 \AA was added above the slab. During geometry optimization, the bottom two atomic layers were fixed, while all other atoms and adsorbates were allowed to relax until the force on each atom was less than 0.01 eV \AA^{-1} . A convergence criterion of $1 \times 10^{-5}\text{ eV/atom}$ was used for structural optimization. Brillouin zone integration was performed using a $2 \times 2 \times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack grid with a Methfessel-Paxton smearing width (σ) of 0.2 eV . Due to the presence of localized $3d$ states on Mn, the electronic structure of Mn was treated within the DFT + U formalism with a U-J parameter of 4.00 eV ⁴⁶. In addition, to account for weak interactions within the catalyst, van der Waals corrections were incorporated using the DFT-PBE-D3 method⁴⁷. Further details regarding

the DFT calculation methods are provided in the Supplemental Information.

Data availability

The data presented in the figures and the key findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request. Source data are provided with this paper.

References

1. Guo, X. et al. Direct, nonoxidative conversion of methane to ethylene, aromatics, and hydrogen. *Science* **344**, 616–619 (2014).
2. Chen, R. & Weng, G. Sustainable energy resources for driving methane conversion. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **13**, 2301734 (2023).
3. Zhang, Q., Kang, J. & Wang, Y. Development of novel catalysts for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis: tuning the product selectivity. *Chem-CatChem* **2**, 1030–1058 (2010).
4. Kosinov, N. & Hensen, E. J. M. Reactivity, selectivity, and stability of zeolite-based catalysts for methane dehydroaromatization. *Adv. Mater.* **32**, e2002565 (2020).
5. Song, S. et al. A selective Au-ZnO/TiO₂ hybrid photocatalyst for oxidative coupling of methane to ethane with dioxygen. *Nat. Catal.* **4**, 1032–1042 (2021).
6. Li, Z. et al. Direct methane activation by atomically thin platinum nanolayers on two-dimensional metal carbides. *Nat. Catal.* **4**, 882–891 (2021).
7. Peter, M. & Mark, T. J. Platinum metal-free catalysts for selective soft oxidative methane → ethylene coupling. Scope and mechanistic observations. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **137**, 15234–15240 (2015).
8. Arinaga, A. M., Ziegelski, M. C. & Marks, T. J. Alternative oxidants for the catalytic oxidative coupling of methane. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **60**, 10502–10515 (2021).
9. Si, J. et al. Oxidative coupling of methane: examining the inactivity of the MnO_x - Na_2WO_4 /SiO₂ catalyst at low temperature. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **61**, 202117201 (2022).
10. Dimitrakopoulos, G., Koo, B., Yildiz, B. & Ghoniem, A. F. Highly durable C₂ hydrocarbon production via the oxidative coupling of methane using a BaFe_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_{3-δ} mixed ionic and electronic conducting membrane and La₂O₃ catalyst. *ACS Catal.* **11**, 3638–3661 (2021).
11. Scapinello, M., Delikonstantis, E. & Stefanidis, G. D. The panorama of plasma-assisted non-oxidative methane reforming. *Chem. Eng. Process.* **117**, 120–140 (2017).
12. Chen, G., Tu, X., Homm, G. & Weidenkaff, A. Plasma pyrolysis for a sustainable hydrogen economy. *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **7**, 333–334 (2022).
13. Delikonstantis, E., Scapinello, M. & Stefanidis, G. D. Low energy cost conversion of methane to ethylene in a hybrid plasma-catalytic reactor system. *Fuel Process. Technol.* **176**, 33–42 (2018).
14. Chang, T. et al. Post plasma catalysis for the removal of acetaldehyde using Mn–Co/HZSM-5 catalysts. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **58**, 14719–14728 (2019).
15. Xu, Chao & Tu, X. Plasma-assisted methane conversion in an atmospheric pressure dielectric barrier discharge reactor. *J. Energy Chem.* **22**, 420–425 (2013).
16. Brandenburg, R. Dielectric barrier discharges: progress on plasma sources and on the understanding of regimes and single filaments. *Plasma Sources Sci. T.* **26**, 053001–053029 (2017).
17. Nozaki, T., Hattori, A. & Okazaki, K. Partial oxidation of methane using a microscale non-equilibrium plasma reactor. *Catal. Today* **98**, 607–616 (2004).
18. Zhang, X. et al. Synergy between β -Mo₂C nanorods and non-thermal plasma for selective CO₂ reduction to CO. *Chem.* **6**, 3312–3328 (2020).

19. Wang, Y. et al. Shielding protection by mesoporous catalysts for improving plasma-catalytic ambient ammonia synthesis. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **144**, 12020–12031 (2022).
20. Sourav, S. et al. New mechanistic and reaction pathway insights for oxidative coupling of methane (OCM) over supported $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ catalysts. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **60**, 21502–21511 (2021).
21. Fleischer, V., Steuer, R., Parishan, S. & Schomäcker, R. Investigation of the surface reaction network of the oxidative coupling of methane over $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{Mn}/\text{SiO}_2$ catalyst by temperature programmed and dynamic experiments. *J. Catal.* **341**, 91–103 (2016).
22. Wang, P., Zhao, G., Wang, Y. & Lu, Y. MnTiO_3 -driven low-temperature oxidative coupling of methane over TiO_2 -doped $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ catalyst. *Sci. Adv.* **3**, e1603180 (2017).
23. Arndt, S. et al. $\text{Mn-Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ as catalyst for the oxidative coupling of methane. What is really known? *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* **425**, 53–61 (2012).
24. Zhang, Y., Wang, H., Zhang, Y. & Bogaerts, A. Formation of microdischarges inside a mesoporous catalyst in dielectric barrier discharge plasmas. *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **26**, 054002 (2017).
25. Zhang, Q. & Bogaerts, A. Propagation of a plasma streamer in catalyst pores. *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27**, 35009–35019 (2018).
26. Guisnet, M. & Magnoux, P. Organic chemistry of coke formation. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* **212**, 89–96 (2001).
27. Schwach, P., Pan, X. & Bao, X. Direct conversion of methane to value-added chemicals over heterogeneous catalysts: challenges and prospects. *Chem. Rev.* **117**, 8497–8520 (2017).
28. Wu, J., Li, S., Niu, J. & Fang, X. Mechanistic study of oxidative coupling of methane over $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ catalyst. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* **124**, 9–18 (1995).
29. Takanahe, K. & Iglesia, E. Mechanistic aspects and reaction pathways for oxidative coupling of methane on $\text{Mn}/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ catalysts. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **113**, 10131–10145 (2009).
30. Zhao, M., Ke, S., Wu, H., Xia, W. & Wan, H. Flower-like $\text{Sr-La}_2\text{O}_3$ microspheres with hierarchically porous structures for oxidative coupling of methane. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **58**, 22847–22856 (2019).
31. Deschenaux, C. et al. Investigations of CH_4 , C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 dusty RF plasmas by means of FTIR absorption. *J. Phys. D Appl. Phys.* **32**, 1876–1886 (1999).
32. Moussa, S. et al. Nature of active nickel sites and initiation mechanism for ethylene oligomerization on heterogeneous Ni-beta catalysts. *ACS Catal.* **8**, 3903–3912 (2018).
33. Silvi, B. & Perchard, J. P. Spectres de vibration et coordonnées normales de quatre espèces isotopiques de propène. *Spectrochim. Acta. A. Spectrosc.* **32**, 11–22 (1976).
34. Heracleous, E., Lemonidou, A. A. & Lercher, J. A. Mechanistic features of the ethane oxidative dehydrogenation by in situ FTIR spectroscopy over a $\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* **264**, 73–80 (2004).
35. Li, P. & Ng, L. M. Surface chemistry of alkyl and perfluoro ethers: a FTIR study of adsorption and thermal desorption of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{F}_5)_2\text{O}$ on SiO_2 . *Surf. Sci.* **342**, 359–369 (1995).
36. Stijn, H., Maryam, A. & Bogaerts, A. Plasma-based CH_4 conversion into higher hydrocarbons and H_2 modeling to reveal the reaction mechanisms of different plasma sources. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **124**, 7016–7030 (2020).
37. Wang, Y. et al. Bimetallic single atom/nanoparticle ensemble for efficient photochemical cascade synthesis of ethylene from methane. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **63**, e202407791 (2024).
38. Chala, S. A. et al. Selective electroreduction of CO_2 to ethanol via cobalt–copper tandem catalysts. *ACS Catal.* **14**, 15553–15564 (2024).
39. Kohn, W. & Sham, L. J. Self-consistent equations including exchange and correlation effects. *Phys. Rev.* **140**, A1133–A1138 (1965).
40. Hohenberg, P. & Kohn, W. Inhomogeneous electron gas. *Phys. Rev.* **136**, B864–B871 (1964).
41. Kresse, G. G. & Furthmüller, J. J. Efficient iterative schemes for aAb initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set. *Phys. Rev. B* **54**, 11169 (1996).
42. Zheng, J. et al. First-principles study of native point defects in hafnia and zirconia. *Phys. Rev. B* **75**, 104112 (2007).
43. Perdew, J. P. & Wang, Y. Pair-distribution function and its coupling-constant average for the spin-polarized electron gas. *Phys. Rev. B* **46**, 12947–12954 (1992).
44. Zhu, Y. et al. 2D Co-doped MnCr_2O_4 nanosheets as efficient bifunctional cathode materials for long-life Li-O_2 batteries. *Inorg. Chem. Front.* **10**, 4252–4265 (2023).
45. Zou, S. et al. Surface coupling of methyl radicals for efficient low-temperature oxidative coupling of methane. *Chinese J. Catal.* **42**, 1117–1125 (2021).
46. Abbas, S. A. et al. Spinel-type Na_2MoO_4 and Na_2WO_4 as promising optoelectronic materials: first-principle DFT calculations. *Chem. Phys.* **538**, 110902 (2020).
47. Xie, Z. et al. Interfacial active sites for CO_2 assisted selective cleavage of C–C/C–H bonds in ethane. *Chem.* **6**, 2703–2716 (2020).

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Author contributions

C.L., K.L., X.T. and H.W. conceived the idea and designed the experiments. C.L. and R.X. synthesized and evaluated the catalysts, performing catalyst characterization and analysis. Y.W. and C.L. performed plasma diagnostics and in situ plasma-coupled FTIR characterization and analysis. D.T. performed the DFT calculations. R.W., S.X. and W.L. conducted the XAFS characterization and analysis. C.L., K.L. and X.T. wrote the paper. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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